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DIRECTIONS OF EXPRESSION OF NATIONAL ISSUES IN THE BURHANI-HAQIQAT JOURNAL

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НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ВЫРАЖЕНИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВОПРОСОВ В ЖУРНАЛЕ “БУРХАНИ-ХЭГИКЯТ”

Abstract

The journal *Burhani-Haqiqat* served as an example of expressing national awakening and socio-political processes in the Caucasus through the press during the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The journal highlighted national issues, the ideas of enlightenment, the role of women in society, and social justice, while simultaneously performing a critical function against the manipulation and censorship observed in the Russian imperial press. The primary targets of criticism in the journal's pages included ideological manipulation, violence, the distortion of ideals in practice, and the quality of literary expression. Consequently, the activities of *Burhani-Haqiqat* hold significant importance for the development of Azerbaijani public thought, the formation of national consciousness, and the promotion of ideals of freedom.

Резюме

Журнал *Bürhani-həqiqət* служил примером выражения национального пробуждения и социально-политических процессов на Кавказе через прессу в конце XIX – начале XX века. Журнал освещал национальные вопросы, идеи просвещения, роль женщин в обществе и социальную справедливость, одновременно выполняя функцию критики манипуляций и цензуры, наблюдавшихся в имперской российской прессе. Основными объектами критики на страницах журнала были идеологические манипуляции, насилие, искажение идеалов на практике и качество литературного выражения. Следовательно, деятельность *Bürhani-həqiqət* имеет важное значение для развития общественной мысли Азербайджана, формирования национального самосознания и продвижения идеалов свободы.

Key words: *Burhani-Haqiqat*, national issues, Caucasus, censorship, women's role in society, ideological manipulation, freedom and liberty

Ключевые слова: *Бурхани-Хакыкат*, национальные вопросы, Кавказ, цензура, роль женщин в обществе, идеологическая манипуляция, свобода и независимость.

At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, profound socio-political processes were unfolding in the Caucasus and Azerbaijani society. As a result of Tsarist Russia's colonial policies, national freedoms were restricted, and the local population lived under harsh socio-economic conditions. On the other hand, the spread of enlightenment ideas, the arrival of European liberal thought in the Caucasus, and the reformist movements within the Turkic-Islamic world created a basis for the political awakening of the national intelligentsia. During this period, the press became an essential tool in shaping public consciousness. Furthermore, with the rising importance of issues of national identity, language, and religion among Muslim peoples, the role of periodicals grew significantly.

In this context, the journal *Burhan-i Haqiqat* began publication. Its establishment was, on the one hand, the result of the demand for national and social revival; on the other hand, it was a product of the political atmosphere shaped by the revolutionary

movements within the Russian Empire, particularly the Revolution of 1905. Although censorship of the press still existed, certain relaxations during this period allowed intellectuals greater opportunities in their struggle for freedom of expression.

On the pages of *Burhan-i Haqiqat*, issues such as social injustice, the defense of national rights, enlightenment, and reformist ideas were widely discussed. This demonstrates that the journal functioned not only as a literary and artistic organ but also as a socio-political platform. Therefore, it became an instrument for expressing national awakening, modernization efforts, and ideals of liberty in the history of Azerbaijani social thought. The first issue of the journal was published on January 1, 1917, under the editorial leadership of Ali Hajizeynalabdinzade Rahimov (Ali Mahzun) as director and editor-in-chief, with Hasan Mirzazade Aliyev serving as publisher.

The emergence of such a publication precisely in Iravan – a city with a rich cultural heritage, artisanal traditions, an enlightened intelligentsia, and a literary

milieu—was considered a significant event not only for local public life but also for the history of Azerbaijani press in general. The fact that its the first issue was sent to press organs in Tbilisi and Baku indicates its regional importance. Although there is no precise and detailed information in the sources regarding the cessation of *Burhan-i Haqiqat*, it is known that the journal was published only during the first half of 1917 and released a total of nine issues (1).

Research on *Burhan-i Haqiqat* remains relatively scarce. Ismayil Mammadov, who later served as executive secretary and final editor of the newspaper *Sovet Ermenistani* (*Soviet Armenia*), defended the first candidate dissertation on this subject in 1972 (2, p. 82). Mirza Bala Mammadzade conducted studies on the history of the Azerbaijani press and provided information on the publishers, editors, period of activity, and objectives of *Burhan-i Haqiqat*. More recently, Dr. Shafaq Nasir has analyzed the journal's activities and significance in the contemporary context. She also carried out its transliteration and publication.

Located in the city of Iravan, the Blue Mosque (*Göy Məscid*) was built in the mid-18th century and entered history as a prominent example of Azerbaijani architecture. At present, however, this religious and architectural monument is presented as the only surviving functioning mosque on the territory of Armenia.

The mosque was restored in the mid-1990s at the initiative of the Iranian government and, since 1996, has once again served as a religious and cultural center. According to an agreement reached between the Armenian state and Iran, the mosque complex has been leased to the Islamic Republic of Iran for 99 years beginning in 2015. Today, alongside religious ceremonies, Persian language courses, cultural events, and a library are also functioning there.

Official institutions in Armenia and local tourism sources predominantly present the Blue Mosque as the “Persian Mosque.” This approach has been criticized in Azerbaijani scholarly and public circles as an attempt to falsify the monument's national and cultural identity. Azerbaijani sources emphasize that the Blue Mosque has historically been an integral part of the religious and cultural heritage of the Azerbaijani people and one of the key elements of the Islamic architectural landscape of Iravan. In fact, a glance at history reveals that Persians never lived in Iravan; the mosque belongs to Azerbaijanis. The issue of the Iravan Mosque remains topical today. Already in 1917, Armenians attempted to falsify history by trying to erase the mosque's historical identity.

In the issue of *Burhan-i Haqiqat* dated January 1, 1917, an article titled *Iravan Mosque* signed under the pseudonym “Tahvil” criticized such distortions. The article refers to the journal *Solntse Rossii* (No. 279), where a depiction of this mosque was presented under the name “Van Mosque.” The attribution of both the authorship of the article and the image to “Ter-yan” was not accidental. Such misrepresentations, on the one hand, indicate the unprofessionalism of the press, and, on the other, reflect a dismissive attitude toward Muslim culture.

A similar case was observed in *Ogonyok*, where a square located at the head of Vorontsov Street in Tbilisi was published with the caption “Market Square in Erzurum.” This confirms that such falsifications were systematic in Russian periodicals. The central accusation raised in the *Burhan-i Haqiqat* article is that such distortions aimed to deceive Russian Muslims and to ignore their historical and cultural heritage. The mislabeling of the Blue Mosque in Iravan as the “Van Mosque” is not merely a geographical mistake but also a distortion of cultural identity. This case may be evaluated as an example of how imperial journalism manipulated information for political purposes. The publication of the Blue Mosque's depiction under the name “Van Mosque” stands as evidence of the Russian press's biased approach toward Muslim heritage. Such practices reveal, on the one hand, journalistic incompetence, and, on the other, intentional distortions serving political and ideological goals. Their exposure is of crucial importance both in the history of the Azerbaijani press and in the study of the cultural heritage of the Caucasus:

“Indeed! Ter-yan's publication of this photograph of the Iravan Mosque under the name ‘Van Mosque’ in *Solntse Rossii*, printed on postcards and circulated throughout the Caucasus and Russia, was nothing less than treating the entire Russian Muslim population as blind, was it not?” (4, p. 29).

The misrepresentation of photographs with false captions in journals such as *Solntse Rossii* and *Ogonyok* illustrates the press's neglect of factual accuracy. Thus, the target of criticism is also the manipulation policy of the imperial media.

In the same issue, a poem titled *Muntakhabat*, published under the signature “F.E.” depicts scenes symbolizing happiness, liberty, and purity. However, the poet emphasizes that these beauties do not correspond to the harsh realities of life. The critique lies in the assertion that living innocently, blissfully, and unaware of suffering is possible only in imagination. In reality, social life is a fragmented and chaotic sphere shaped by needs, sorrows, and passions. Here, the target of criticism is the gap between idealized conceptions of life and reality. By employing descriptions of beauty, spring gardens, and spiritual elevation, the author points to the contradictions inherent in social existence.

In the issue of *Burhan-i Haqiqat* dated January 20, 1917, an article entitled *On Literature*, published under the pseudonym “Muallim Naji,” targeted the modes of expression in literary and artistic creativity from the perspective of qualitative evaluation. The author emphasized that clarity, simplicity, and comprehensibility—forms of expression accessible to the general public—were necessary virtues. The criticism was directed against convoluted and obscure expressions that rendered meaning opaque in writing. By employing the notion of *sadedilaneh* (simplicity), the author highlighted both purity and, at the same time, the use of hidden meaning and irony—thus positioning it against dry and superficial descriptions. *Incelik* (fineness) was presented as a quality that, by conveying multilayered meanings, ensures depth and aesthetic

appeal of thought; in this way, the author criticized shallow and simplistic modes of thinking.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the development of the Azerbaijani press faced numerous socio-political and technical obstacles, the most significant of which was the issue of censorship. The publishing experience of *Burhan-i Haqiqat* serves as a vivid example of this problem. In the issue dated March 25, 1917, in a note entitled *To Our Esteemed Readers*, the author wrote that the journal's publication was carried out under the difficult conditions of a lack of printing houses, the absence of typesetters, and paper shortages. Yet, the heaviest obstacle was censorship. Since no censorship office had been established in the city by the autocratic government, the editorial board was forced to send press materials in separate sheets to Tiflis for approval. This analysis of *Burhan-i Haqiqat* demonstrates that censorship in the history of the Azerbaijani press was not merely an ideological barrier but also a practical one. It restricted freedom of expression and hindered the press from fulfilling its essential public functions.

The theme of women has always held both religious and socio-philosophical significance within the Turkic-Islamic milieu. In literary texts, the image of the woman was at times presented as the bearer of spiritual values, and at other times as the ornament of life and the pillar of society. The text in question synthesizes various reflections and aphorisms about women in a poetic manner, elucidating her role in life.

In the issue dated April 15, 1917, a poem entitled *Among Turkish-Islamic Women*, published under the signature "Fatma Khanim," begins by collecting various ideas regarding the significance of women for humanity. The common conclusion of the authors was that woman is indispensable for the existence of humankind and the continuity of the universe. Verses such as "Could the universe exist if deprived of woman?" emphasize that the absence of women would entail the disappearance of humanity itself. This underscores that woman constitutes the foundation of existence not only biologically but also spiritually. In the continuation of the text, woman is portrayed as the most beautiful remedy on the mountain of life, a being who breathes vitality into the body of existence. In her laughter, in her face radiating hope and joy, a light of happiness appears for humanity. This perspective presents woman as the guardian of both the continuity of nature and the moral harmony of life.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the socio-political situation in the Caucasus was marked by tensions. Confrontations in ethno-national relations, alongside violence and looting, placed the Muslim population in constant danger. In the issue of *Burhan-i Haqiqat* dated May 7, 1917, a text was published in an ironic tone under the expression "the contribution prepared by Armenian soldiers for liberty and equality." Here, the ideals of "liberty and equality" are shown to have been distorted in practice and transformed into violence. The looting of Muslim houses in Taza village demonstrated the scale of the events. The killing of an innocent Kurd in Shor village was presented as a typical example of ethnic violence.

The brutal beating of Mashadi Qafar and Abbasali Akhundov in Turkmenli village further deepened social tensions. The shooting of a Muslim near Pishik Ark intensified the public trauma, while the searching of Muslim houses in Tepabashi created a constant atmosphere of fear in people's daily lives. The author used the word "contribution" (*tohfe*) in a satirical sense to criticize the type of "gift" that violence was bringing to society. The final metaphor, "orphaned chick," symbolized the defenseless, unprotected, and abandoned condition of the Muslim community. This image reflected the weakness and isolation of the community in the face of political developments. Consequently, the text not only enumerated instances of violence but also functioned as a social critique of the falsification of liberty and equality ideals.

On May 31, 1918, public figure Akbar Akbarov, together with several Muslims, was brutally beaten by Armenian soldiers. Although Akbarov called for reconciliation with the words, "let there be no talk of Armenian and Muslim—we are all brothers," his appeal was instead met with further violence. Several Muslims participating in the incident were also beaten, while Akbarov was taken unconscious to the committee. The promises of the committee members that "measures would be taken" served merely as superficial consolation.

In reality, the duty of the Armenian soldiers was to subject Muslims to insult and violence, while the responsibility of the executive committee was to pacify them with empty promises. In the streets, markets, and boulevards of Iravan, hundreds of Muslims were humiliated daily. The fact that Muslims were absent from public spaces after 8 p.m. indicated that they lived under conditions of fear and pressure (5, p. 284).

In an article titled *Azadlıqımı* ("Is It Freedom?"), signed "A.M." in the journal, editor Ali Mahzun Zeynalabdinzade Rahimov raised the paradoxical question, "Is it freedom or is it slavery?" The primary target of criticism was the brutality of Armenian soldiers and the passive, formal attitude of the Transcaucasian Executive Committee. At the same time, the slogans of "liberty" (*hurriyyat*) and "equality" (*musavat*) were sharply criticized for being distorted in practice and turned into the enslavement of Muslims. The editor thus defined "contribution" in the lexicon as: "Contribution—on the occasion of liberty, the gift given every day by freedom-loving Armenian soldiers to many Iravan Muslims in the form of beatings" (4, p. 136). By this usage, the editor inverted the word "contribution," which normally has a positive meaning, to expose the daily physical and social violence inflicted upon Muslims under the guise of liberty. Likewise, he defined "liberty" as "a portion of happiness (beating) given by Armenian soldiers to Iravan Muslims" (4, p. 156). The central critique was thus aimed at the violence committed under the name of "freedom-loving" ideals and the distortion of these ideals into their opposite—oppression and humiliation of Muslims.

The analysis of *Burhan-i Haqiqat* demonstrates that the press did not merely serve literary and aesthetic functions, but also acted as a socio-political platform.

By focusing on issues of nationality, enlightenment ideas, and social justice, the journal contributed to the development of Azerbaijani public thought and national awakening. The analyses also reveal that the journal faced significant difficulties: censorship barriers, shortages of printing facilities and paper, and the limited resources of the editorial staff all had a serious impact on its activity. At the same time, the journal became an important source for understanding the preservation of national identity, the role of women in society and spirituality, as well as the expression of social justice and liberty in Iravan and the Caucasus more broadly.

In the journal, the targets of criticism were defined across various aspects: ideological manipulation – the distortion of Muslim heritage and the use of geographical-cultural misrepresentations by the press of the Russian Empire, as well as by certain newspapers and journals; violence against society – the coercion and oppression inflicted upon Muslims by Armenian soldiers under the guise of “devotion to liberty”; the distortion of ideals in practice – the transformation of concepts such as “freedom” and “liberty” into forms of enslavement and humiliation for the Muslim population; and the expression of thought in literature – the critique of literary methods that failed to provide simplicity and subtlety, as well as objections against convoluted expressions that created misunderstanding among readers.

In conclusion, *Burhan-i Haqiqat* journal was not merely a historical document or literary source, but also a significant socio-political platform for the development of Azerbaijani public thought, the articulation of national awakening, and the promotion of the ideals of freedom. The journal constitutes an important example in the history of Azerbaijani press, both in terms of preserving historical facts and exposing ideological distortions.

References

1. Nasir Sh. İrəvanda Azərbaycan mətbuatı: 95 yaşlı “Bürhani-həqiqət” jurnalı. – *525-ci qəzet*, 24 January 2012.
2. Bayramov İ. Qədim Azərbaycan şəhəri İrəvan. – Ankara: İksad Yayınları, 2023.
3. Nasir Sh. İrəvanda Azərbaycan mətbuatı: “Bürhani-həqiqət” jurnalı. – *Ədəbiyyat qəzeti*, 8 January 2024. – Əlaqə: <https://edebiyatqazeti.az/news/science/11223-irevanda-azerbaycan-metbuati-burhani-heqiqet-jurnali>
4. “Bürhani-həqiqət”. – “3 sayılı Bakı mətbəəsi” ASC, 2017. – 172 p.
5. Paşayeva (Hüseynova) A. “Azərbaycan” jurnalında publisistika məsələləri (1953–2010). – Bakı: Elm və təhsil, 2010.
6. Hüseynova Aynura. *Ermənilərin Ağrı yalanları akademik çalışmalarda*. – II Uluslararası Oğuz Boyları Sempozyumu bildirilər kitabı, Kayseri: 15 December 2022, p. 283–294.